

Optimizing Dark Data for ESG Compliance: the Case of the Logistic Sector

Angelo Leogrande, LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro: leogrande.culture@lum.it

Abstract

Optimizing dark data for ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) compliance is a strategic opportunity for companies in the logistics and warehouse sectors. Dark data, or unutilized information generated during daily operations, can provide crucial insights to improve sustainability, social responsibility, and governance transparency. This paper explores how advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Internet of Things (IoT) can be leveraged to analyze vast amounts of unstructured data, transforming it into actionable insights. By employing these technologies, organizations can reduce carbon emissions through optimized energy management, improve safety and working conditions, and ensure compliance with evolving regulations. The paper emphasizes that proper data mapping and integration are the first steps to harnessing dark data. AI-driven predictive analytics can identify inefficiencies in energy use or transportation, while IoT sensors provide real-time monitoring to enhance resource efficiency and reduce waste. Additionally, dark data can improve governance practices by enabling more accurate ESG reporting, thereby strengthening corporate transparency and stakeholder trust. However, the paper also highlights challenges, including the unstructured nature of dark data and the technological investments required to process it effectively. Organizations must develop a systematic approach to integrating dark data into decision-making processes to ensure compliance with ESG standards and improve overall operational efficiency. By doing so, companies can not only enhance their competitive advantage but also contribute to a more sustainable future.

JEL CODE: L9; L91; L97, L98; L99.

Keywords: Dark Data, ESG, Warehouse Management, Logistics, Artificial Intelligence.

1. Introduction

In the contemporary business landscape, the integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles has become a crucial element for ensuring long-term sustainability, ethical responsibility, and transparent governance. These principles are not only gaining prominence due to regulatory demands but are also being increasingly prioritized by investors, consumers, and other stakeholders who are concerned about the environmental and social impacts of corporate activities. In this context, the optimization of "dark data" — the vast reservoir of unstructured and underutilized information generated by companies during routine operations — represents a strategic opportunity for organizations aiming to enhance their ESG compliance.

The Rise of ESG as a Business Imperative. ESG compliance has shifted from being a peripheral concern to a central component of corporate strategy. Companies are now required to actively demonstrate how their business practices align with sustainable and ethical standards, which in turn can significantly influence their reputation, risk profile, and overall market competitiveness. The growing demand for responsible corporate behavior, fueled by increasing global awareness of environmental challenges and social inequalities, has led to the development of stringent regulations that govern aspects such as carbon emissions, labor rights, and corporate transparency. For example, frameworks like the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) and the Corporate

Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) are establishing new benchmarks for reporting and transparency in ESG practices.

Understanding Dark Data: An Untapped Resource. In parallel with the rise of ESG, the digitalization of business processes has resulted in the exponential growth of data. However, a significant portion of this data — often referred to as "dark data" — remains untapped, residing in emails, documents, sensor logs, social media interactions, and various unstructured formats. It is estimated that dark data can account for over 80% of an organization's total data assets, yet it remains largely unutilized, often due to its complexity or the lack of appropriate tools for its analysis. The failure to harness this information represents a missed opportunity, particularly in the context of ESG, where deeper insights into operations, supply chains, and stakeholder interactions could lead to more effective compliance and enhanced sustainability initiatives. Dark data holds the potential to reveal hidden inefficiencies, identify opportunities for resource optimization, and enhance transparency across a company's value chain. For instance, data collected from Internet of Things (IoT) devices installed in warehouses can be analyzed to optimize energy use, reduce waste, and ensure compliance with environmental standards. Similarly, internal communications data can provide insights into corporate culture and labor practices, helping companies align their social strategies with ESG objectives.

The Role of Advanced Technologies in Dark Data Optimization. To unlock the value embedded within dark data, companies are increasingly turning to advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and predictive analytics. These tools offer the ability to process large volumes of unstructured data, identify patterns, and generate actionable insights that can be directly applied to improving ESG compliance. AI and ML, in particular, have been recognized for their ability to enhance decision-making by predicting future trends, detecting inefficiencies, and optimizing operations. For instance, AI-driven energy management systems can analyze historical data to predict periods of high energy consumption in warehouses and propose adjustments that reduce both costs and carbon emissions. Moreover, the use of Natural Language Processing (NLP), a subset of AI, can enable companies to analyze text-heavy data such as supplier contracts, social media interactions, or internal reports to ensure compliance with social and governance standards.

Dark Data and ESG: A Strategic Fit. The optimization of dark data presents a compelling opportunity for businesses striving to meet their ESG goals. First, by leveraging dark data, companies can gain a more nuanced understanding of their environmental impact, identifying areas where waste can be reduced or where resources can be utilized more efficiently. For example, sensor data from logistics operations can reveal inefficiencies in fuel consumption, leading to the optimization of transportation routes and a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions. Second, dark data analysis can support the "social" component of ESG by providing insights into labor conditions and human rights issues within the supply chain. Monitoring internal and external communications, as well as supplier data, allows companies to detect potential risks related to unethical practices or labor violations, and to take corrective action before these issues escalate. Finally, in terms of governance, dark data can enhance transparency by enabling more accurate and timely reporting of ESG metrics. Companies can integrate data from diverse sources into a centralized system, ensuring that their ESG reporting is comprehensive, consistent, and compliant with regulatory requirements. Blockchain technology, in particular, offers a promising solution for tracking and verifying ESG-related data, as it ensures data integrity and traceability throughout the supply chain.

Challenges and Opportunities in Dark Data Utilization. Despite its potential, the utilization of dark data for ESG purposes is not without challenges. One of the primary barriers is the complexity associated with processing unstructured data. Many organizations lack the infrastructure or expertise required to analyze and integrate dark data into their decision-making processes. Moreover, issues related to data privacy and security can further complicate the use of dark data, particularly in

industries where sensitive information must be handled with care. However, as technologies continue to evolve, these challenges are becoming increasingly surmountable. Cloud computing, for example, provides scalable and cost-effective solutions for storing and analyzing vast amounts of data, while advancements in AI and ML are making it easier to extract meaningful insights from complex datasets. As companies continue to invest in digital infrastructure and develop the necessary data governance frameworks, the optimization of dark data for ESG compliance will become more accessible and impactful. The intersection of dark data optimization and ESG compliance represents a critical frontier for businesses seeking to enhance their sustainability efforts, improve operational efficiency, and build stronger relationships with stakeholders. By leveraging advanced technologies to harness the potential of dark data, companies can transform previously untapped information into a strategic asset that drives better environmental, social, and governance outcomes. As the pressure for greater transparency and accountability continues to grow, those organizations that successfully integrate dark data into their ESG strategies will be well-positioned to lead in a rapidly evolving global marketplace.

The article continues as follows: the second section presents a literature review, the third section presents a definition of dark data, the fourth section presents an application of the ESG compliance in logistics and warehouse management, the fifth section affords the question of the challenged of dark data in logistics, the sixth afford the question of the optimization of dark data for ESG compliance, the seventh section analyses the technology to unlock the potential of dark data, the eight section afford the question of the implementation of dark data optimization for ESG, the ninth section analyses the question of the benefits of dark data optimization for ESG, the tenth section concludes.

2. Literature

2.1 Dark Data, Data-Driven Innovations, and Technological Impact on Sustainability

Archer's (2021) article examines the use of data-driven sustainability approaches within global supply chains and introduces the concept of "surveillable space." This term refers to how the increasing use of data, particularly in the name of sustainability, enables heightened surveillance and control within supply chains. By leveraging data for tracking environmental and social impacts, corporations can both comply with regulations and improve their sustainability profiles. However, Archer critically analyzes how this data-driven approach may also reinforce power imbalances and control over workers and suppliers, particularly in developing countries. The paper emphasizes the tension between data use for positive sustainability outcomes and the potential for exploitation and surveillance, raising ethical concerns about the broader implications of data-centric governance in global supply chains. Buchholz, et al., (2022) delve into the use of big data to track risks in the mineral raw material markets. Their study provides a comprehensive analysis of how real-time data collection and analysis can enhance supply chain risk management, particularly in sectors characterized by high volatility, such as mineral markets. The authors argue that big data offers significant advantages in monitoring fluctuations in supply and demand, geopolitical risks, and environmental issues. This improves the resilience of supply chains and helps organizations mitigate risks more effectively. The paper suggests that real-time risk tracking, enabled by advanced data analytics, can transform the management of supply chains in industries dependent on raw materials, ensuring more robust risk mitigation and resource allocation. Alrakhis (2023) presents a master's thesis focused on the implementation of smart sensing technologies, providing insights into the operational benefits and challenges associated with this technology. Smart sensing refers to the use of sensors and data

processing tools to collect and analyze information from physical environments in real-time. The thesis explores how smart sensing can optimize operational efficiency, particularly in sectors like logistics and infrastructure, where real-time data is essential for decision-making. However, the paper also points out challenges such as data security and the complexity of integrating these systems into existing infrastructures, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive understanding of both the technical and organizational aspects of smart sensing deployment. Chung's (2022) doctoral dissertation explores the fusion of data and blockchain technology in lowering investment barriers for sustainable infrastructure. By combining hedonic pricing models and blockchain, Chung proposes a framework for enhancing transparency, reducing costs, and improving investor confidence in sustainable infrastructure projects. The integration of these technologies provides a way to create verifiable and tamper-proof records of infrastructure performance, which in turn lowers the risks associated with long-term investments. Chung's work highlights the potential of blockchain to revolutionize the infrastructure sector by offering a more reliable and efficient mechanism for funding and managing projects aimed at sustainability. Denev and Amen's (2020) explores how alternative data sources—ranging from satellite imagery to social media activity—are reshaping investment strategies. The authors argue that alternative data, when combined with traditional financial metrics, can offer investors a more nuanced understanding of market trends and risks. This book provides practical insights for investors, traders, and risk managers looking to harness the power of non-traditional data in making more informed decisions. The work underscores the growing importance of alternative data in financial markets, particularly in the context of rapidly changing global economic conditions.

In their 2024 article, Dong et al. examine the role of corporate digital innovation in mitigating climate change, specifically within the context of China. The authors argue that corporate digital innovation is a key driver in accelerating climate change mitigation. Their research emphasizes how digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and big data, enable corporations to optimize energy use, reduce carbon footprints, and create innovative business models that align with sustainability goals. Through empirical evidence, the authors highlight that the adoption of such technologies can expedite corporate contributions to national and global climate goals, potentially making significant strides in decarbonizing industries and enhancing corporate efficiency. However, they also note the challenges of balancing these innovations with costs and potential disruptions to existing systems, indicating that effective implementation requires strategic planning and coordination between corporations and policymakers. Gu and Guo (2023) delve into the alienation of project digital responsibility, providing a critical examination through the lenses of Fraud Risk Factor Theory and Information Asymmetry Theory. The authors propose that digital responsibility, particularly in project management, can become alienated or misaligned with core business values due to information asymmetry between management and stakeholders. When there is an imbalance of information, it can lead to unethical practices, mismanagement, and ultimately, fraud. Their work suggests that for digital responsibility to be genuinely integrated into a business framework, transparency and accountability must be emphasized, as these factors reduce the risk of alienation and support ethical governance. The theoretical approach taken by Gu and Guo helps broaden the understanding of digital responsibility within modern corporate governance, especially in the context of complex, data-driven projects. In contrast, Gu et al. (2024) explore ESG reporting within the framework of smart cities, emphasizing the need for government-led ESG initiatives. Their work highlights the critical role that accurate and comprehensive ESG reporting plays in fostering sustainability and accountability in urban environments. As smart cities increasingly rely on technology for urban planning, energy management, and public services, the authors argue that ESG reporting should be at the forefront of governance efforts. This ensures that smart city initiatives not only drive technological innovation but also maintain a commitment to environmental and social

responsibility. By focusing on government ESG reporting, this study offers a framework for integrating sustainability into the digital infrastructure of cities, making it clear that transparency in ESG reporting is essential for the success of smart city models. Fregonese's (2023) work focuses on the integration of blockchain and allied technologies into global value chains to support sustainability efforts. The author argues that blockchain technology can enhance transparency and traceability in supply chains, thereby reducing environmental and social risks. Blockchain's ability to securely record transactions in a decentralized ledger system is particularly useful in industries such as mining, agriculture, and manufacturing, where sustainability issues are prominent. Fregonese suggests that the adoption of blockchain technology in these sectors can lead to more sustainable global value chains by ensuring that every step in the supply chain complies with ESG standards. This approach provides a practical solution to the challenges of tracking and managing sustainability data across complex, multinational supply chains. Khan and Millner (2023) provide a practical guide to people analytics, highlighting the power of data-driven approaches in human resource management. Their book emphasizes how leveraging big data and analytics can improve decision-making in HR, from recruitment to performance management. By implementing people analytics, companies can make more informed decisions that align with broader corporate strategies, including those related to sustainability and ethical labor practices. The authors also address the ethical implications of data use in HR, cautioning that companies must ensure data transparency and employee privacy to avoid potential misuse.

Kneppers (2021) explores the development of a data-driven Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) tool for a Dutch bank, focusing on performance analysis and the exclusion of controversial investments. The thesis highlights the critical role of CSR in enhancing corporate accountability and responsibility, particularly in the financial sector. Kneppers emphasizes the importance of data analytics in identifying potentially controversial activities of clients, allowing financial institutions to align their investment decisions with sustainability goals. The study showcases how CSR can be integrated into core banking functions, ultimately pushing the bank towards more ethical investments. Kneppers' tool suggests a shift in how data-driven decision-making can steer financial institutions toward more socially responsible investment strategies. Lee et al. (2024) present a comprehensive framework that integrates Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles with Artificial Intelligence (AI). Their study underscores the growing relevance of AI in assessing and managing ESG-related risks and opportunities. The authors propose a responsible AI framework that seeks to balance AI's efficiency and automation with the ethical implications of its use in corporate governance. The framework is designed to ensure that AI technologies do not compromise sustainability efforts but rather enhance transparency and accountability. By integrating ESG factors into AI assessments, companies can align their technological innovations with broader sustainability and ethical goals, thereby improving their long-term sustainability performance. Liu et al. (2024) address the paradoxical nature of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) in promoting green transformation within enterprises. The article highlights how IIoT technologies can drive significant environmental benefits through improved efficiency and resource management, but at the same time, they present new challenges in terms of data management and security. The authors argue that while IIoT enables companies to reduce their environmental footprint, the proliferation of interconnected devices and data flows can create vulnerabilities, leading to privacy issues and increased cyber risks. Thus, the IIoT is viewed as a "double-edged sword" that must be carefully managed to maximize its potential for driving sustainable industrial transformation. Mahlendorf et al. (2023) examine the innovative use of data in management accounting, providing examples of how new data analytics tools are transforming accounting practices. The study focuses on how data-driven approaches are being applied to performance measurement, cost management, and decision-making processes in organizations. The authors argue that the integration of big data and analytics in management

accounting is helping companies to better track and predict financial outcomes, optimize resource allocation, and improve overall business performance. Their research shows that data-use cases are expanding the traditional role of accounting, pushing it towards a more strategic and forward-looking function within organizations. Olsson and Zhi (2024) investigate the impact of digitalization on sustainability performance in Northern European manufacturing firms. Their research highlights how the adoption of digital technologies is enabling firms to improve their environmental and social performance by streamlining operations and reducing resource use. Digitalization is portrayed as a key driver of sustainability, offering companies the tools to monitor and optimize their environmental impact. However, the study also points out that the successful implementation of digital technologies depends on the company's capacity to adapt to new digital infrastructures and integrate these tools into their core business processes.

The article by Radulescu et al. (2024) presents a novel approach to mineral identification for sustainable resource extraction by employing a hybrid deep learning-enabled FinTech model. The authors emphasize that accurate mineral identification is critical in optimizing resource extraction while maintaining environmental sustainability. The integration of FinTech with deep learning offers a cutting-edge solution to traditional identification challenges, enabling more precise extraction with less environmental impact. This approach aligns with the increasing need for technological solutions that support sustainability in resource-heavy industries, underlining how advanced data processing models can promote efficient and responsible extraction practices. Rana et al. (2023) explore the role of analytics in accounting and auditing, providing an introduction to how data analytics is reshaping these fields. The authors highlight the growing reliance on data-driven insights in enhancing the transparency, accuracy, and efficiency of accounting practices. Analytics not only streamline financial processes but also provide more robust auditing frameworks that ensure regulatory compliance and reduce the risk of errors or fraud. The integration of analytics into accounting and auditing points toward a future where big data and machine learning models will further revolutionize how financial data is managed, audited, and interpreted. Rasool and Dulhare (2022) address the pressing issue of data center security, a crucial concern in today's data-driven world. The authors outline the vulnerabilities present in data centers, which store and manage vast amounts of sensitive information. They emphasize the need for robust security measures, including encryption, access control, and real-time monitoring, to mitigate the risk of cyberattacks. As data centers are central to operations in nearly every sector, ensuring their security is paramount in protecting not only private data but also the integrity of entire businesses and industries. The paper highlights how increasing the resilience of these centers is critical for maintaining trust in digital infrastructure. Seidl (2022) explores the concept of corporate digital responsibility (CDR), focusing on how companies can foster human-centric innovation while building trust in the digital landscape. The article argues that as digital transformation accelerates, businesses must prioritize ethical practices in their technological strategies. CDR goes beyond compliance, demanding that companies consider the societal and environmental impacts of their digital operations. This perspective is increasingly important in a world where digital technologies are pervasive, and the way they are used can have profound effects on both people and the planet. The paper highlights the need for organizations to balance innovation with responsibility, ensuring that technological advancements benefit all stakeholders. Wu et al. (2022) present a study on unsupervised neural networks for spatial-temporal analytics, focusing on data authenticity in environmental smart reporting systems. Their work underscores the importance of ensuring data integrity in environmental monitoring, where accurate data is critical for decision-making. By leveraging advanced neural network models, the authors demonstrate how data authenticity can be maintained in real-time, even in complex environmental reporting scenarios. This approach is crucial in promoting transparency and accountability in sustainability initiatives, where the accuracy of reported data directly influences environmental policies and practices. Yliranta (2023)

discusses the role of data-driven performance optimization in supply chain management, highlighting the power of tools like Power BI in streamlining operations and improving decision-making. The paper illustrates how real-time data analytics can provide businesses with valuable insights that enhance performance, reduce costs, and increase sustainability. By focusing on data-driven strategies, companies can optimize their supply chains to be more responsive and sustainable, a key consideration in today's increasingly competitive and environmentally conscious markets. Vänskä et al. (2024) take a different approach by examining the intersection of data leaks and sustainable fashion. The article highlights the potential for data breaches in online shopping and the fashion industry's move towards more sustainable practices. As online shopping grows, so does the risk of sensitive consumer data being exposed. The authors argue that addressing these data security concerns is essential to maintaining consumer trust and promoting sustainable business models in fashion. This paper is particularly relevant in an era where consumers are becoming more conscious of both the ethical practices of the companies they support and the security of their personal information. Tuladhar et al. (2024) explore the use of blockchain for compliance in supply chains, particularly in sourcing conflict minerals. The authors present blockchain as a powerful tool for ensuring transparency and traceability in supply chains, which is vital for regulatory compliance and ethical sourcing. The case study demonstrates how blockchain can be applied to monitor the sourcing of conflict minerals, ensuring that companies meet legal and ethical standards. This approach is particularly valuable in industries where supply chains are complex, and the risk of unethical practices is high. Blockchain technology, with its immutable records, offers a solution to these challenges by providing verifiable and transparent supply chain data.

2.2. ESG Models and Governance

Alexa (2023) focuses on the Task Force on Climate-Related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) and its application in sustainability reporting, using the case study of Normet Group Oy. The TCFD provides a framework for companies to disclose how climate-related risks and opportunities impact their financial health, helping investors make informed decisions. Alexa's handbook emphasizes the importance of transparency in corporate sustainability reporting and the practical application of TCFD guidelines. The case study provides real-world insights into how companies like Normet Group Oy integrate TCFD principles into their reporting processes, ensuring that they meet both regulatory requirements and investor expectations. This reference highlights the growing relevance of TCFD in aligning corporate reporting with global sustainability goals and ensuring that companies manage climate risks effectively. Becker, et al. (2024) address the development of a framework to monitor finance for green investments, a critical aspect of achieving global sustainability objectives. The Joint Research Centre report emphasizes the need for robust tools to track green financial flows, ensuring that investments are aligned with environmental sustainability goals. The authors explore different metrics and monitoring mechanisms that could be used to assess the impact of green investments, contributing to a more transparent and accountable financial ecosystem. This work is particularly relevant given the increasing importance of sustainable finance in the global economy, as governments and corporations seek to meet climate goals and transition to greener energy sources. The proposed framework aims to bridge the gap between financial reporting and environmental performance, helping policymakers and investors track the effectiveness of green investment strategies. Brusseau (2023) delves into the human impact of AI, particularly in the context of ethical investing in AI-intensive companies. The article highlights the challenges and opportunities

associated with integrating AI into corporate governance, especially in terms of sustainability. Brusseau argues that as AI continues to reshape industries, it is essential for companies to adopt ethical frameworks that consider the social and environmental implications of AI technologies. This approach underscores the need for a new model of ethical investing that goes beyond traditional financial metrics, focusing instead on the broader societal impacts of AI. Brusseau's work is particularly important in the current technological landscape, where AI is increasingly being deployed in ways that could both enhance and undermine sustainability efforts. Cerrato Garcia (2024) discusses the regulatory landscape of sustainable finance in the European Union (EU), with a focus on the challenges and imperatives of enforcing sustainability financial promises. The article highlights the fragmented nature of EU regulations and the need for harmonized private enforcement mechanisms to ensure that companies adhere to their sustainability commitments. Cerrato Garcia's analysis emphasizes the role of regulatory frameworks in promoting transparency and accountability in sustainable finance, while also addressing the legal challenges that arise from inconsistencies in the application of these regulations across different EU member states. This work is crucial for understanding how regulatory environments shape corporate behavior and influence the effectiveness of sustainability initiatives in the financial sector. Comoli et al. (2023) present a systematic literature network analysis of ESG accounting under disruptions. The article examines how disruptions, such as economic crises or global pandemics, impact ESG accounting and reporting practices. The authors argue that ESG metrics are increasingly becoming essential for assessing corporate performance, especially during periods of uncertainty. Their analysis provides a comprehensive overview of how companies can adapt their ESG reporting to reflect changing circumstances, ensuring that their sustainability efforts remain transparent and accountable even in times of disruption. This work underscores the resilience of ESG frameworks and their ability to provide valuable insights into corporate sustainability performance, even in challenging economic conditions.

Daniel, et al., 2021 article delves into the role of stakeholder influences on ESG governance, reporting, and profitability within the global automotive industry supply chain. The automotive industry, with its complex supply chain and large environmental footprint, is under increased scrutiny for its sustainability practices. The authors highlight how stakeholders, such as investors, regulators, and consumers, influence corporate decisions related to ESG governance. They argue that companies with strong ESG governance and transparent reporting practices tend to exhibit better profitability, as they align more closely with stakeholder expectations. By embedding ESG factors into their core business strategy, automotive companies not only enhance their financial performance but also build stronger relationships with their stakeholders. This research emphasizes the increasing importance of stakeholder-driven ESG initiatives in shaping corporate governance and financial outcomes in resource-intensive industries like automotive manufacturing. Duman and Kongar (2023) focus on ESG modeling and the prediction of uncertainty in electronic waste management. As electronic waste (e-waste) continues to rise due to rapid technological advancements, managing this waste sustainably has become a critical concern. The authors explore how ESG factors can be integrated into models that predict the uncertainties associated with e-waste generation and management. This study highlights the importance of ESG frameworks in addressing not only environmental concerns but also the social and governance issues related to e-waste. The article's focus on uncertainty modeling is particularly relevant in understanding the complexities of e-waste, which is difficult to manage due to the unpredictable nature of technological obsolescence and the associated environmental hazards. This research underscores the necessity for businesses to develop more accurate ESG models to manage and mitigate the impacts of electronic waste effectively. Dygas (2024) provides an overview of ESG doctrine application in business management across Europe and Asia, two regions with distinct regulatory frameworks and business cultures. The paper explores how companies in these regions apply ESG principles and the variations in governance, transparency, and reporting practices.

While Europe has been at the forefront of ESG regulation, particularly with initiatives like the European Green Deal and the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), Asia is rapidly catching up, with countries like Japan and China emphasizing sustainability in business management. Dygas highlights that while regulatory pressure is a key driver of ESG adoption in Europe, market competitiveness and investor demand are the primary forces in Asia. This comparative analysis provides valuable insights into how regional differences shape the implementation of ESG practices, showing that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to ESG governance. Feng, et al., (2023) focus on environmental information transparency and its role in fostering green innovations. The authors argue that greater transparency in environmental data encourages businesses to adopt more sustainable practices and fosters innovation in green technologies. By making environmental data more accessible and understandable, companies are pressured to innovate in ways that reduce their environmental footprint. This research highlights the importance of transparency as a catalyst for green innovation, suggesting that companies that disclose their environmental impact are more likely to develop and implement sustainable innovations. The paper demonstrates that transparency is not just about compliance but can also be a strategic tool for driving innovation and competitiveness in green technologies. Funk, et al., (2024) explore the predictive capacity of ESG sentiment on official ratings using a few-shot learning perspective. This paper highlights the role of machine learning in analyzing ESG sentiment from textual data and how it can predict future ESG ratings. By leveraging advanced data analytics, the authors propose that ESG sentiment, derived from unstructured data such as news articles and reports, can offer valuable insights into a company's future ESG performance. This research emphasizes the growing importance of AI and machine learning in ESG analysis, suggesting that sentiment analysis can complement traditional ESG rating methods and provide a more dynamic, real-time understanding of a company's sustainability trajectory.

Galina (2022) examines the potential effects of ESG policies on the returns of investment portfolios. This study sheds light on the growing trend of integrating ESG factors into investment decisions. As ESG considerations become more significant in the financial world, investors are increasingly using these criteria to evaluate the sustainability and ethical impact of their investments. Galina's work suggests that incorporating ESG factors can enhance long-term financial returns by mitigating risks related to environmental degradation, social unrest, or governance failures. The paper highlights the increasing pressure on companies to adopt sustainable practices that align with investors' expectations for responsible investing. Furthermore, it points out that ESG-focused portfolios tend to be more resilient in the face of market volatility, emphasizing the financial as well as ethical benefits of such policies. Grajales and Albanés Uribe (2024) focus on the intersection of ESG policies and financial performance, particularly in the context of mining technology in Latin America. Their study explores whether Multilatinas—large multinational companies from Latin America—contribute to the region's sustainability through their adoption of ESG frameworks. This analysis is particularly important for sectors like mining, where environmental and social impacts are significant. The authors argue that ESG-driven initiatives can improve the financial performance of these companies by ensuring better resource management, reducing operational risks, and aligning with global sustainability standards. However, the study also acknowledges the uncertainties posed by advanced mining technologies, which may present both opportunities and challenges in the pursuit of sustainable development. This article underscores the complexity of implementing ESG policies in industries with a traditionally high environmental footprint. Gu, et al., (2023) investigate the application of ESG frameworks in the port industry, specifically in China. Their empirical analysis of sustainable port development reveals how ESG policies can be implemented to reduce the environmental impact of port operations, enhance social welfare, and improve governance practices. The study emphasizes the importance of environmental management in ports, which are often significant sources of pollution. By adopting ESG frameworks, ports can better manage their carbon

footprints, improve working conditions, and comply with governance standards. The authors highlight that such efforts not only contribute to sustainability but also improve operational efficiency, thus benefiting the financial performance of port authorities. This research illustrates how ESG frameworks can be tailored to specific industries, addressing both their challenges and opportunities. Fourie (2023) explores the future of environmental risk considerations in the banking sector, focusing on how banks are responding to the growing importance of environmental sustainability. The study argues that banks are increasingly incorporating environmental risks into their lending and investment decisions to mitigate potential financial losses related to climate change and environmental degradation. Fourie discusses how environmental risk management is becoming a key component of ESG policies in the banking sector. The paper points out that banks that fail to consider these risks may face reputational damage, regulatory penalties, and financial losses. Therefore, the incorporation of environmental risk assessments into banking practices is essential for the sector's long-term sustainability. Hardyment (2024) provides an in-depth exploration of how ESG data is measured and interpreted, focusing on the challenges of standardizing ESG metrics across different industries and regions. This work is crucial for understanding how businesses and investors make sense of ESG data in the context of measuring corporate responsibility and performance. Hardyment emphasizes the need for clear and consistent ESG data to enable better decision-making and accountability. The article points out that without standardized metrics, companies and investors face difficulties in comparing ESG performance across different entities. This paper is a call for improved methodologies to measure and interpret ESG data accurately, helping businesses align with sustainability goals while ensuring transparency for stakeholders.

Karia (2022), in her master's thesis, investigates the creation, pricing, and modeling of ESG derivatives, a relatively new financial instrument designed to promote sustainable investments. The study highlights the complexity involved in pricing these derivatives, given that traditional financial models do not account for non-financial factors like environmental and social impact. Karia addresses this gap by proposing models that incorporate ESG criteria into derivative pricing. The thesis emphasizes that the growing demand for ESG-linked products reflects a shift in investor behavior, as they increasingly prioritize sustainability alongside financial returns. This work underscores the need for innovation in financial modeling to accommodate the evolving priorities of socially responsible investing, providing a foundation for further exploration into how ESG factors can be quantified and priced in the financial markets. Lee et al. (2022) contribute to the understanding of how ESG factors influence the implementation of clean development mechanisms (CDMs) through an institutional approach. Their study explores the intricate relationship between institutional governance and ESG practices, particularly in the context of clean energy projects. The authors argue that the success of CDMs, which are projects aimed at reducing carbon emissions in developing countries, is heavily dependent on institutional support and governance structures that prioritize ESG factors. By employing an institutional framework, the study demonstrates how policies and governance systems can either facilitate or hinder the adoption of sustainable practices. This research provides valuable insights into how ESG considerations can be institutionalized to promote sustainable development, particularly in emerging markets where regulatory frameworks may still be evolving. Kocabey Ciftci (2024) presents a comprehensive analysis of factors influencing environmental performance through a fuzzy cognitive map (FCM) model. Her work focuses on the concept of a "dark green enterprise," which refers to businesses that prioritize environmental sustainability to a greater extent than their competitors. By using FCM, the study maps out the complex interplay of factors that contribute to environmental performance, offering a nuanced view of how businesses can achieve sustainable development goals. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of the causal relationships between various ESG factors and environmental outcomes, highlighting the importance of strategic decision-making in pursuing sustainability. The study's use of FCM also demonstrates the value of

advanced analytical tools in assessing the multifaceted nature of environmental performance, particularly in the context of long-term sustainability planning. Leventi (2022) examines the expanding role of ESG criteria in investment decisions, underscoring the increasing importance investors place on sustainability. The paper highlights how ESG factors are no longer considered peripheral to financial performance but are now central to assessing the overall risk and return profile of investments. Leventi's work suggests that the integration of ESG into investment decisions has become a competitive advantage for firms, as investors are more likely to favor companies that demonstrate strong environmental and social responsibility. This shift is driven by growing awareness of the financial risks associated with poor ESG practices, such as regulatory penalties, reputational damage, and the impact of climate change on business operations. The paper advocates for further adoption of ESG criteria in investment analysis, reflecting the broader trend towards sustainable finance. Li and Wang (2024) explore how ESG strategies can provide a procurement advantage during disruptive times. Their work highlights that companies with strong ESG frameworks are better positioned to adapt to disruptions, such as supply chain crises or environmental regulations, due to their focus on long-term sustainability. The study argues that ESG-driven firms are more resilient, as their strategic emphasis on governance and sustainability enables them to navigate uncertainties more effectively. This paper reinforces the growing consensus that ESG is not just a moral or ethical consideration but also a critical component of corporate strategy and competitiveness in an increasingly volatile global market.

The selected articles explore various dimensions of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) strategies, transformative investment, corporate sustainability disclosures, and their growing role in financial performance and sustainable development. Each study emphasizes the increasing importance of ESG in shaping corporate behavior, regulatory frameworks, and investor decision-making. The studies collectively demonstrate the transition from traditional financial metrics to a more comprehensive evaluation that includes non-financial factors such as environmental sustainability and social responsibility.

Napolitano (2023) offers a critical analysis of the evolution of ESG frameworks and their limitations in the face of a rapidly changing global environment. The study explores the concept of "IRGTM" (Integrated Reporting for Growth and Transformation Management), which the author argues is an advancement beyond traditional ESG frameworks. Napolitano posits that IRGTM integrates financial, environmental, and social metrics in a more holistic manner, providing companies with a strategic toolkit for not only surviving but thriving in a world where sustainability is becoming a critical business imperative. He emphasizes that while ESG has gained global relevance, its standards often fall short of addressing the full complexity of today's business challenges. IRGTM, in contrast, provides a more dynamic and future-oriented framework, helping businesses to align their operations with the demands of a global economy increasingly focused on sustainability and resilience. This perspective broadens the debate on sustainability by suggesting that ESG frameworks need to evolve to meet the challenges of the 21st century.

O'CONNOR-WILLIS (2021) takes a practical approach to understanding how companies can effectively implement ESG strategies. The paper provides a blueprint for integrating ESG into corporate governance and day-to-day operations. The study outlines several key steps for companies looking to make their ESG commitments actionable, including creating clear governance structures, aligning ESG goals with broader corporate objectives, and ensuring that sustainability initiatives are backed by robust data and reporting mechanisms. O'CONNOR-WILLIS emphasizes that for ESG to be successful, it cannot be treated as a standalone initiative but must be deeply embedded into the corporate fabric, influencing everything from risk management to stakeholder engagement. The study highlights the importance of leadership commitment and organizational culture in driving ESG success. Without these, the risk is that ESG initiatives will be superficial or purely symbolic,

providing little actual value in terms of sustainability or financial performance. Penna, Schot, and Steinmueller (2021) explore the field of sustainability investing, mapping the evolution of transformative investment practices. Their work highlights how investment strategies are shifting from purely financial considerations to those that account for social and environmental impact. The authors focus on "transformative investment," which aims to drive systemic change by redirecting capital into industries and technologies that promote sustainability. They argue that transformative investment is critical for achieving global sustainability goals, such as the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The study points out that while there has been significant growth in sustainability investing, the sector still faces challenges, particularly around measurement and accountability. Investors need more reliable tools to assess the long-term impact of their investments on sustainability outcomes. The authors call for the development of better metrics and reporting standards to ensure that transformative investments genuinely contribute to sustainability.

Raghupathi, et al. (2023) focus on corporate sustainability disclosures, particularly as they are reported in Securities Exchange Commission (SEC) filings. The study examines the quality and transparency of these disclosures and how they influence corporate behavior. The authors find that while there is increasing pressure for companies to disclose their ESG activities, the quality of these disclosures varies significantly. Many firms provide only minimal information, often lacking the depth required for investors to make informed decisions about a company's sustainability practices. The paper highlights the need for regulatory reforms to standardize ESG disclosures, ensuring that they are not only consistent but also comprehensive. The authors argue that without more robust disclosure requirements, ESG reporting risks becoming a "box-ticking" exercise rather than a genuine reflection of corporate sustainability efforts.

Saini et al. (2022) conduct a scientometric analysis of non-financial disclosures, examining their role in promoting sustainable development. The study provides a quantitative assessment of research trends in non-financial reporting, with a particular focus on how these disclosures contribute to sustainability. The authors find that there has been a significant increase in academic interest in non-financial disclosures, driven by the growing recognition that financial metrics alone are insufficient for evaluating corporate performance in a sustainable context. Their analysis suggests that non-financial disclosures, such as ESG reports, are critical for stakeholders—including investors, regulators, and consumers—who are increasingly concerned with the broader social and environmental impact of businesses. The study underscores the need for more comprehensive and transparent non-financial reporting frameworks to support sustainable development.

Secic (2023) investigates the impact of ESG disclosure on the underpricing and financial performance of initial public offerings (IPOs). The study finds that companies with higher levels of ESG disclosure tend to experience less underpricing, suggesting that transparency around ESG practices can reduce the perceived risk of new market entrants. Furthermore, the study shows that firms with strong ESG credentials are likely to perform better in the long run, as investors increasingly prioritize sustainability in their decision-making processes. This paper contributes to the growing body of evidence suggesting that ESG is not only a moral imperative but also a strategic advantage that can enhance financial performance.

Singhania and Saini (2022) present a case study on Reliance Industries, demonstrating how a systems approach to ESG can drive long-term corporate success. The study emphasizes the need for an integrated ESG strategy that aligns with the company's broader business goals. By analyzing Reliance Industries, the authors show that ESG can be a source of competitive advantage, enabling companies to navigate regulatory challenges, improve stakeholder relations, and enhance operational efficiency. This case study highlights the importance of leadership in embedding ESG principles into the corporate strategy and provides practical insights into how businesses can leverage ESG for sustainable growth.

Smiles and Purcell (2023) focus on sustainable investing and the inherent challenges and opportunities within ESG frameworks. The authors explore the growing demand for sustainable

investments and discuss the complexities that arise when investors attempt to balance profitability with sustainability goals. One of the key challenges they identify is the difficulty of standardizing ESG metrics across industries and regions, making it hard for investors to accurately assess a company's ESG performance. The lack of uniformity in ESG reporting also contributes to "greenwashing," where companies misrepresent their sustainability efforts. Despite these challenges, the authors point to significant opportunities for investors who can navigate these complexities, such as the potential for long-term returns driven by socially responsible companies. Smiles and Purcell highlight that as ESG investing continues to evolve, there is an increasing need for more robust, transparent, and comparable ESG metrics that investors can rely on to make informed decisions. Torres and Lönnqvist (2024) examine the role of Nordic private equity firms in sustainable investments and sustainable value creation. Their study underscores how private equity firms in the Nordic region are uniquely positioned to drive sustainability through their investments, given the region's strong regulatory framework and cultural commitment to environmental and social responsibility. The authors argue that private equity firms can play a pivotal role in integrating ESG criteria into the businesses they invest in, thereby promoting sustainable development. The paper highlights that sustainable value creation goes beyond environmental impact; it also includes social contributions such as job creation and improvements in working conditions. However, Torres and Lönnqvist also acknowledge that private equity firms face significant challenges in balancing short-term financial returns with long-term sustainability goals. Despite these obstacles, the authors conclude that private equity firms can be a driving force in the transition towards a more sustainable economy if they prioritize ESG integration in their investment strategies. Trotta, et al., (2024) provide a bibliometric perspective on the linkages between FinTech and ESG, exploring how financial technology can enhance ESG implementation. Their study identifies FinTech as a powerful enabler of sustainable finance, particularly through innovations such as blockchain, digital payments, and AI-driven analytics. These technologies can improve transparency, efficiency, and accessibility in ESG reporting and investments. For instance, blockchain can be used to track and verify supply chain data, ensuring that companies meet their sustainability targets. The authors highlight that FinTech has the potential to revolutionize the ESG landscape by making it easier for businesses and investors to measure, manage, and report on sustainability metrics. However, they also caution that the rapid pace of technological advancement in FinTech could outstrip the development of regulatory frameworks, potentially leading to new challenges in ensuring accountability and ethical practices. Tse et al. (2024) explore the impact of AI on ESG investing, with a focus on Nexus FrontierTech, an AI company. The authors argue that AI can significantly enhance ESG investing by improving data collection, analysis, and decision-making processes. AI-driven systems can process vast amounts of data more efficiently than traditional methods, enabling investors to make more informed decisions about the sustainability of their investments. However, the authors also raise concerns about the ethical implications of using AI in ESG investing. They argue that while AI can improve the accuracy and efficiency of ESG assessments, it also risks reinforcing existing biases in data and decision-making processes. The study emphasizes the need for robust governance frameworks to ensure that AI is used responsibly in ESG investing, highlighting the potential for AI to either enhance or undermine sustainability efforts depending on how it is implemented. Yue et al. (2024) explore the integration of ESG principles into supply chain management in small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The authors identify several factors that influence the successful implementation of ESG in supply chains, including leadership commitment, stakeholder pressure, and access to resources. They argue that SMEs, despite their limited resources compared to larger corporations, can still play a crucial role in promoting sustainability through their supply chain practices. The study highlights the importance of collaboration between SMEs and their suppliers to ensure that ESG principles are embedded throughout the supply chain. Additionally, Yue et al. emphasize the need for government support and

incentives to help SMEs overcome the financial and logistical barriers to ESG implementation. The authors conclude that with the right support and commitment, SMEs can contribute significantly to global sustainability goals by adopting more responsible supply chain practices. Wong et al. (2021) discuss strategies for building environmental transparency and accountability, emphasizing the importance of clear and consistent communication of environmental performance to stakeholders. The authors argue that businesses must not only comply with regulatory requirements but also go beyond them by proactively disclosing their environmental impact. The study highlights the role of technology in enhancing environmental transparency, particularly through the use of digital platforms that allow for real-time reporting and monitoring of environmental performance. Wong et al. also point out that building environmental transparency requires a cultural shift within organizations, where sustainability becomes an integral part of business strategy rather than an afterthought. The authors conclude that companies that prioritize transparency and accountability in their environmental practices are more likely to build trust with stakeholders and achieve long-term success.

2.3 Corporate Responsibility, Governance, and Ethical Practices

Capasso and Ferraris (2021) provide a comparative analysis of CSR approaches in the apparel industry, focusing on two major corporations, VF Corporation and PVH Corporation. The study highlights the different strategies these companies adopt to integrate corporate social responsibility into their operations. VF Corporation, known for brands such as The North Face and Timberland, emphasizes a long-term commitment to sustainability through environmentally friendly materials and responsible sourcing. On the other hand, PVH Corporation, which owns brands like Calvin Klein and Tommy Hilfger, has taken significant steps in promoting labor rights and reducing environmental impact in its supply chain. This case study provides valuable insights into how large corporations in the apparel industry balance profitability with ethical responsibility, showing that effective CSR is not one-size-fits-all but requires tailored strategies that align with each company's business model and stakeholder expectations. Burcă et al. (2024) delve into the complex relationship between corporate financial performance (CFP) and corporate sustainability performance (CSP), focusing on the tension between earnings management and process improvement. The article argues that companies often face a trade-off between short-term financial goals and long-term sustainability objectives. Earnings management can distort the true financial health of a company, leading to practices that may undermine long-term sustainability efforts. However, the authors also point out that process improvement initiatives—such as investments in sustainable technology or supply chain enhancements—can simultaneously enhance both financial and sustainability performance over time. This dual focus on financial metrics and sustainability underscores the growing recognition that businesses must integrate sustainability into their core strategies to remain competitive in the long run. Gatti and Chiarella (2020) examine the challenges and opportunities for investors and asset managers in the infrastructure sector, particularly in the face of industry disruption. The article highlights how changes in technology, regulation, and environmental considerations are reshaping the infrastructure sector, creating both risks and opportunities for investors. The authors emphasize the need for asset managers to adapt their strategies to incorporate sustainability and resilience into their investment decisions. Infrastructure projects, often capital-intensive and long-term, are increasingly scrutinized for their environmental impact and contribution to sustainable development. This paper offers a comprehensive overview of how the infrastructure sector is evolving in response to these pressures, providing valuable insights for investors seeking to align their portfolios with sustainability goals. Kano and Ciravegna (2024) explore the contribution of Alain Verbeke to

international business scholarship, particularly in the area of governance for sustainability. The authors reflect on Verbeke's work in shaping the discourse around how multinational enterprises (MNEs) can transition towards more sustainable business practices. The article emphasizes the importance of governance structures that promote sustainability, arguing that MNEs must go beyond mere compliance with environmental regulations and actively pursue sustainability as a strategic objective. The tribute volume highlights Verbeke's influence on the field, particularly his focus on the role of governance in ensuring that businesses not only "talk the talk" but also "walk the walk" when it comes to sustainability. Puteri (2024) discusses the legal and regulatory measures needed to reduce the digital carbon footprint in Indonesia. The paper highlights the growing environmental impact of digital technologies, particularly the energy consumption of data centers and digital infrastructure. Puteri argues for stronger legal frameworks that incentivize businesses to adopt more sustainable digital practices, such as using renewable energy and optimizing data usage. The paper underscores the importance of aligning digital transformation with sustainability goals, showing that as Indonesia's digital economy grows, so too must its efforts to mitigate the associated environmental impacts.

Seidl (2022) examines the concept of Corporate Digital Responsibility (CDR), focusing on how companies can promote human-centric innovation while building trust in the digital age. The article underscores the increasing importance of ethical digital practices in a world where data is a powerful asset. As businesses become more data-driven, the risks associated with data misuse, privacy violations, and unethical AI applications grow. Seidl argues that companies must adopt responsible digital strategies that prioritize the well-being of individuals and society. This approach requires transparency, accountability, and ethical governance structures that ensure digital innovations benefit all stakeholders. By fostering trust in digital tools and processes, companies can build stronger relationships with consumers and improve their long-term sustainability. Trevathan (2024) offers a detailed analysis of financial accounting within the broader context of the business environment through case studies. This article delves into the intricacies of accounting practices, particularly in light of changing regulatory and economic landscapes. Trevathan highlights the importance of robust financial reporting in ensuring that businesses remain accountable to their stakeholders. The study emphasizes that as financial regulations become more stringent, companies must adapt their accounting practices to meet these new demands. The article also explores how accounting strategies can align with broader business objectives, such as sustainability and corporate governance, thereby enhancing overall corporate performance. Through the use of case studies, Trevathan provides practical insights into how businesses can navigate the complex world of financial reporting while maintaining ethical standards. Verbeke, et al., (2022) explore the complex dynamics of international business strategy, addressing both the bright and dark sides of multinational enterprises (MNEs). The authors argue that while MNEs have the potential to drive positive global change, particularly in areas such as sustainability and technological innovation, they can also contribute to significant social and environmental harm. The "full canvas" approach outlined in the paper encourages companies to consider the broader implications of their business strategies, from ethical supply chain management to environmental impact. The study offers a nuanced perspective on international business practices, demonstrating that MNEs must balance profitability with social responsibility. Verbeke et al. highlight the importance of governance in ensuring that businesses operate ethically and sustainably in a globalized economy. Vries (2023) discusses the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), which aims to bridge the gap between corporate sustainability practices and reporting standards. The article emphasizes the need for more rigorous sustainability reporting frameworks to ensure that companies provide accurate and comprehensive information about their environmental and social impacts. Vries highlights that many businesses still struggle to meet these reporting standards, resulting in a lack of transparency and accountability. By implementing the CSRD,

companies will be required to adopt more robust sustainability reporting practices, thereby improving transparency and fostering trust among stakeholders. This article is particularly relevant as investors and consumers increasingly demand greater accountability from businesses regarding their environmental and social footprints. Zafeiriou et al. (2023) address the pressing issue of corruption and illicit activities in the financial sector, proposing a hybrid methodological approach to mitigate these risks. The authors explore various strategies for combating corruption, emphasizing the importance of regulatory frameworks, robust governance, and transparency in financial institutions. The study highlights how corruption undermines trust in the financial system and hinders economic development. By adopting comprehensive anti-corruption measures, financial institutions can enhance their credibility and contribute to a more stable and transparent economic environment. This research is critical in light of the ongoing challenges faced by financial sectors worldwide in mitigating illicit activities.

2.4 Supply Chain Sustainability and Risk Management

Andeobu, et al., (2022) focus on the extractive sector and its approach to risk management, analyzing how it influences corporate sustainability. The study highlights that companies in the extractive industry—such as mining and oil—face unique risks, including environmental degradation, regulatory pressures, and community opposition. The authors argue that effective risk management in this sector is essential for achieving corporate sustainability. By mitigating operational risks, companies can ensure long-term profitability while addressing sustainability concerns, such as reducing their environmental footprint and promoting community development. The empirical analysis shows that companies that implement robust risk management frameworks are better positioned to meet their sustainability goals, as they can proactively address the challenges associated with their operations. Antony et al. (2023) propose a Design Science Research (DSR) methodology for operational excellence (OPEX) initiatives, emphasizing the importance of a systematic approach to process improvements within organizations. The study explores how organizations can achieve OPEX by integrating DSR into their operational strategies. DSR is a research method that focuses on the development and evaluation of innovative solutions to complex problems, and when applied to operational excellence, it offers a structured approach to continuous improvement. The authors highlight that OPEX initiatives supported by DSR can lead to increased efficiency, reduced waste, and enhanced overall performance. This article is particularly relevant for companies seeking to adopt data-driven methodologies to streamline their operations and ensure long-term sustainability. Faccioli and Mauro (2021) investigate the impact of sustainable strategies on the price returns of funds investing in European assets. The study underscores the growing importance of sustainability in financial markets, as investors increasingly prioritize environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria when making investment decisions. The authors analyze how funds that integrate sustainable strategies tend to perform over time and how they are perceived in the market. Their findings suggest that funds with a focus on sustainability can generate competitive financial returns while promoting long-term environmental and social benefits. This research adds to the growing body of evidence that sustainable investing is not only ethically sound but also financially viable, especially in the context of European markets, where regulatory frameworks are increasingly emphasizing ESG compliance. Fenu (2020) explores the approaches adopted by multinational companies to implement and preserve labor rights across their supply chains. The study highlights the challenges that companies face in maintaining labor standards, particularly in regions where regulations are weak or enforcement is limited. Fenu emphasizes that multinational corporations play a critical role in promoting labor rights by adopting voluntary standards and engaging with local stakeholders to ensure fair working

conditions. The paper also discusses the importance of transparency and monitoring in supply chains to prevent labor rights violations. This article is particularly relevant in the context of global supply chains, where companies are increasingly held accountable for the social and environmental impacts of their operations. Guinchard (2024) provides a comparative analysis of public and private defense investment strategies in the Nordic region, focusing on how these strategies are influenced by geopolitical and economic factors. The article highlights that defense investments are a critical component of national security strategies, particularly in regions with complex geopolitical landscapes like the Nordic countries. Guinchard compares the approaches of public institutions and private companies, revealing the different priorities and risk tolerances that shape their investment decisions. Public investments tend to focus on long-term security and strategic objectives, while private investors are more concerned with profitability and risk management. This comparative analysis offers valuable insights into the intersection of defense, economics, and investment, showing how public and private sectors can collaborate to enhance security while addressing financial and operational risks.

Ivory (2021) examines the stabilization efforts undertaken by the World Bank in emerging markets between 2008 and 2016, highlighting the challenges and successes of these initiatives. The article emphasizes that while World Bank programs were largely effective in providing short-term financial stability, they were also met with numerous challenges, such as political instability, corruption, and inadequate infrastructure. Ivory's assessment underscores the importance of tailoring stabilization efforts to the unique socio-economic conditions of each country. Furthermore, the study suggests that long-term success in emerging markets requires not only financial assistance but also strong governance reforms and capacity-building programs to ensure sustained economic development. This study is particularly relevant in illustrating the complex interplay between international aid and local governance in driving sustainable growth in developing economies. Moumeni and Saber (2023) focus on the use of machine learning to optimize production costs in supply chains, a critical area for businesses seeking to enhance efficiency and competitiveness. The authors argue that by leveraging machine learning algorithms, companies can better predict demand, manage inventory, and optimize production schedules. This leads to significant cost reductions and improved operational efficiency. The article provides case studies that illustrate how machine learning has been successfully applied in various industries, showing that this technology can revolutionize traditional supply chain management by offering real-time data analysis and predictive capabilities. As companies face increasing pressure to improve margins and adapt to fluctuating markets, the use of machine learning in supply chains becomes a key competitive advantage. Palm and Saveborn (2024) explore sustainability initiatives in the road freight logistics industry, an area known for its significant environmental impact due to high fuel consumption and carbon emissions. The authors highlight how logistics companies are adopting sustainability practices, such as using electric vehicles, optimizing routes, and investing in fuel-efficient technologies. These measures not only reduce environmental damage but also result in cost savings and compliance with regulatory standards. The article emphasizes the growing importance of sustainability in logistics, particularly as consumer demand for greener solutions increases. The study also notes that sustainability initiatives in logistics can improve a company's brand reputation and help businesses meet global climate targets. Rangel (2021) discusses the ESG risks in the metal and mineral supply chain, focusing specifically on copper. The study presents a framework for analyzing and mitigating ESG risks in the extraction and supply of metals, which are often associated with environmental degradation, human rights violations, and governance issues. Rangel emphasizes the need for greater transparency and accountability in the metal supply chain, particularly in light of rising global demand for copper, which is essential for many industries, including electronics and renewable energy. The framework proposed in the article helps companies identify and manage ESG risks, ensuring that they can meet both regulatory

requirements and consumer expectations for ethical sourcing. Schuh et al. (2022) argue that suppliers should be central to any business transformation strategy. In their work, they highlight the strategic importance of viewing suppliers not merely as vendors but as integral partners in the business ecosystem. By fostering close relationships with suppliers, companies can drive innovation, reduce costs, and improve product quality. The article emphasizes that businesses that collaborate closely with their suppliers are better positioned to respond to market changes and consumer demands. The authors advocate for a shift in how companies approach supplier management, suggesting that closer integration can result in more resilient and competitive supply chains.

Shbikat (2021) discusses the violation of labor rights in global supply chains, advocating for a multi-stakeholder approach to address these issues. The article highlights how globalization has resulted in complex and often opaque supply chains, making it difficult to ensure compliance with labor standards, particularly in developing countries. Shbikat argues that multinational corporations (MNCs) bear significant responsibility for labor rights violations, as they often source materials and products from countries with weaker labor protections. However, addressing these violations requires the involvement of multiple stakeholders, including governments, NGOs, and labor organizations, in addition to MNCs. The study emphasizes that without collective action and shared accountability, efforts to protect workers in global supply chains will remain ineffective. This multi-stakeholder approach is increasingly recognized as essential for addressing the root causes of labor exploitation, ensuring that all parties involved in the supply chain adhere to ethical standards. Stanisławski and Szymonik (2023) focus on reverse logistics, a process where companies implement strategies to manage the return of goods from consumers back to producers. Their work underscores the importance of reverse logistics as part of broader efforts to promote sustainability and environmental protection in supply chains. The authors highlight how reverse logistics helps companies minimize waste, reuse materials, and reduce their overall environmental impact. This process is particularly relevant in industries such as electronics and manufacturing, where waste and resource use are significant concerns. Stanisławski and Szymonik (2023) emphasize that the implementation of reverse logistics requires a shift in corporate mindset, where sustainability is seen not only as a regulatory obligation but also as a strategic advantage. By adopting reverse logistics, companies can reduce costs, improve efficiency, and meet growing consumer demand for environmentally responsible practices. Tritto and Ricci (2022) examine the development of the SISME model, designed to assess sustainable value for competitive advantage in small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The authors argue that SMEs, despite their size, have a crucial role in driving sustainability in the global economy. The SISME model offers a framework for SMEs to integrate sustainability into their business strategies, helping them achieve competitive advantage by aligning with growing consumer and regulatory demands for responsible business practices. Tritto and Ricci (2022) demonstrate that sustainability is not just a concern for large corporations; SMEs can also benefit from adopting sustainable practices, as these efforts can lead to cost savings, enhanced reputation, and long-term growth. The study highlights that SMEs, often more agile and innovative than larger firms, are well-positioned to lead in sustainability, provided they have the right tools and frameworks in place. Tuladhar et al. (2024) explore the application of blockchain technology to ensure transparency and compliance in conflict mineral sourcing. Conflict minerals, often sourced from regions plagued by armed conflict and human rights abuses, present significant risks for companies that rely on these materials in their products. Tuladhar et al. (2024) argue that blockchain technology, with its immutable and transparent record-keeping capabilities, offers a solution to this challenge by providing traceability throughout the supply chain. The authors present a case study demonstrating how blockchain can be used to monitor compliance with regulations governing conflict minerals, ensuring that companies source materials ethically and transparently. This approach is particularly

valuable in industries such as electronics and automotive, where conflict minerals are widely used, and regulatory requirements for ethical sourcing are stringent.

Macro themes	Literature Review
Dark Data, Data-Driven Innovations, and Technological Impact on Sustainability	Archer, M. (2021); Buchholz, et al., (2022); Alrakhis, (2023); Chung, K. (2022); Denev and Amen (2020); Dong et al., (2024); Gu and Guo, (2023); Gu, et al. (2024); Fregonese, (2023); Khan and Millner (2023); Kneppers, (2021); Lee et al., (2024); Liu, et al., (2024); Mahlendorf, et al., (2023); Olsson and Zhi, (2024); Radulescu et al., (2024); Rana, et al., (2023); Rasool and Dulhare, (2022); Seidl, (2022); Wu, et al., (2022); Yliranta (2023); Vänskä, et al., (2024); Tuladhar, et al., (2024).
ESG Models and Governance	Alexa, (2023); Becker, et al., (2024); Brusseau, (2023); Cerrato Garcia, (2024); Comoli, et al., (2023); Daniel, et al., (2021); Duman, and Kongar (2023); Dygas, R. (2024); Feng, et al., (2023); Funk, et al., (2024); Galina, (2022); Grajales, and Albanés Uribe (2024); Gu, et al., (2023); Fourie (2023); Hardyment (2024); Karia, (2022); Lee, et al., (2022); Kocabay Ciftci, (2024); Leventi, (2022); Li and Wang (2024); Napolitano (2023); O'CONNOR-WILLIS (2021); Penna, et al., (2021); Raghupathi and Raghupathi, V. (2023); Saini et al., (2022); Secic, A. (2023); Singhani and Saini (2022); Smiles and Purcell (2023); Torres and Lönnqvist (2024); Trotta et al., (2024); Tse et al., (2024); Yue et al., (2024); Wong et al., (2021).
Corporate Responsibility, Governance, and Ethical Practices	Capasso and Ferraris (2021); Burcă, et al., (2024); Gatti and Chiarella (2020); Kano and Ciravegna (2024); Puteri, D. S. (2024); Seidl (2022); Trevathan (2024); Verbeke, et al., (2022); Vries, C. (2023); Zafeiriou, et al., (2023).
Supply Chain Sustainability and Risk Management	Andeobu et al. (2022); Antony, et al. (2023); Faccioli and Mauro, (2021); Fenu (2020); Guinchard (2024); Ivory (2021); Moumeni and Saber (2023); Palm and Saveborn (2024); Rangel, (2021); Schuh, et al. (2022); Shbikat, (2021); Stanisławski and Szymonik (2023); Tritto and Ricci (2022); Tuladhar et al. (2024).

3. Dark Data

Dark data is a category of information that organizations generate during their day-to-day operations but, for various reasons, is not fully exploited or utilized in decision-making processes. This data can come from a variety of sources, such as internal employee communications, industrial sensor readings, financial transaction logs, or even information collected by employee performance monitoring systems. In many cases, companies collect a significant amount of this data, but lack the resources, analytical capabilities, or technological infrastructure needed to extract it and transform it into useful knowledge. One of the most challenging aspects of dark data is its widespread distribution within organizations, which makes it difficult to manage and analyze in a systematic way. This is because unstructured data, such as emails or instant messages, often remains haphazardly stored and is not integrated into business intelligence or business analytics systems. Similarly, data collected by sensors in industrial or logistics settings can go unused due to a lack of adequate tools to process it in real time or analyze long-term trends. Despite its abundance, dark data also poses a number of challenges. One of the main issues is the risk of non-compliance with regulations, especially in the context of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) standards. ESG standards are increasingly important for companies, as expectations regarding environmental, social, and governance responsibility are becoming a priority for investors, customers, and regulators. In this context, efficiency in the use of data is key. Dark data can contain valuable information that could be used to improve environmental sustainability, social inclusiveness, or transparency of corporate practices. However, if not properly managed and analyzed, it could represent a missed opportunity or, worse still, a potential risk of non-compliance. For example, in the case of a large company that produces consumer goods, dark data could include information related to energy use in its production facilities. If this data is not analyzed, the company could miss the opportunity to optimize its energy consumption, reduce carbon emissions and, consequently, improve its ESG score. Likewise, data related to employees' working conditions or interactions with local communities could be obscured,

preventing the company from demonstrating its social commitment or avoiding potential litigation. Furthermore, managing dark data also presents operational and technological challenges. Many organizations have not yet adopted the technologies or practices needed to extract value from this data, such as the use of machine learning or artificial intelligence algorithms, which could automate the process of analyzing large volumes of unstructured information. Added to this is the problem of storing and securing dark data. Companies could store huge amounts of data without being aware of its content, which increases the risk of privacy breaches or cyberattacks, especially if this information is not adequately protected. In short, dark data represents both a challenge and an opportunity for modern organizations. If managed properly, they could provide a source of competitive advantage, improve ESG compliance, and enable more informed and sustainable business decisions. On the contrary, if left unexplored, they could become a liability in terms of inefficiency and regulatory non-compliance (Ajis and Baharin, 2019; Hobart, 2020; Munot et al., 2019).

4. ESG Compliance in Logistics and Warehouse Management

In logistics and warehouse management, compliance with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) standards is a crucial element to ensure that operations are not only cost-effective, but also sustainable, ethical, and transparent. Aligning logistics and warehouse operations with these principles involves a direct commitment to reducing environmental impacts, adopting good labor practices, and complying with regulations, thus helping to create value for stakeholders and improve corporate reputation. From an environmental perspective, adopting ESG practices in logistics management involves reducing carbon emissions and optimizing the energy efficiency of operations. For example, a company can monitor energy consumption in its warehouses and implement LED

lighting systems or solar panels to reduce overall energy consumption. Using electric vehicles to transport goods can also reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, optimizing delivery routes and managing inventory more efficiently can help reduce waste, such as product spoilage or excessive use of packaging, which are a significant source of environmental impact. From a social perspective, ESG compliance requires adopting fair and safe working practices. In warehouse and logistics operations, this means ensuring that employees operate in a safe environment and are treated with respect. Companies must also ensure that their suppliers and partners along the supply chain follow ethical practices, ensuring that child labor practices or abusive working conditions are not used. Community engagement can also play an important role, as companies operating in a logistics context often have a direct impact on local communities through the use of infrastructure, job creation and waste management. Implementing ESG policies therefore also means maintaining an open dialogue with communities and ensuring that operations contribute positively to local well-being. From a governance perspective, logistics and warehouse management must comply with applicable regulations, maintaining transparent reporting and responsible data management. This involves not only complying with local and international trade and labor laws, but also ensuring that all operations are traceable and accurately documented. Transparency in reporting helps demonstrate commitment to sustainability and social responsibility, while proper data management ensures that sensitive information, such as customer or employee data, is protected from breaches and used in compliance with privacy regulations. Effective use of dark data can be a valuable resource to improve ESG compliance in all of these areas. Dark data, or untapped information generated by day-to-day operations, can provide valuable insights to optimize logistics and warehouse processes. For example, data collected by sensors on vehicles or machinery can be used to monitor energy consumption and reduce waste. Analysis of internal communications and operational logs can reveal opportunities to improve workplace safety or optimize personnel management. In governance, dark data can help improve transparency in corporate reporting, providing more complete and accurate data on the sustainability of operations. Integrating the use of dark data with an ESG strategy allows companies to improve both operational efficiency and overall sustainability. Through better resource management and in-depth data analysis, organizations can reduce waste, improve employee safety and well-being, and ensure more transparent and accountable governance. This not only optimizes costs and increases competitiveness, but also helps create a more sustainable future for the company and the communities in which it operates (Rodionova et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2023; Kim, et al., 2021; Al Amosh and Khatib, 2023).

5. Challenges with Dark Data in Logistics

Dark data in the logistics and warehouse context comes from a wide range of sources that continuously generate information during daily operations. However, most of this data remains untapped, despite its potential to provide meaningful insights to improve operational efficiency and strategic decision making. One of the challenges of exploiting this data is its unstructured nature, which can make it difficult to extract useful information. The main sources of dark data in this context include vehicle telematics, IoT sensors in warehouses, RFID data from inventory systems, customer communications, maintenance records, and supplier transactions. Vehicle telematics, for example, generates data related to vehicle movements, fuel consumption, maintenance intervals, and road conditions. This data can provide valuable information to optimize routes, reduce energy consumption, and improve preventive maintenance. However, it is often not fully exploited, remaining in a raw and unused state. This is because analyzing this data requires advanced tools that can process large amounts of information and identify relevant patterns. Similarly, IoT (Internet of Things) sensors installed in warehouses produce a huge amount of data regarding temperature, humidity, goods movements and equipment conditions. This data could be used to optimize space management, prevent breakdowns or improve the preservation of sensitive products. However, data often remains disconnected from management systems, and its integration and analysis requires specific skills and advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning. RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) data from inventory systems is another source of dark data. RFID tags track the movements and locations of goods, but the huge volume of data they generate can be difficult to manage and analyze without an adequate strategy. If analyzed correctly, this data could improve inventory management, prevent product loss and optimize delivery times, improving the efficiency of the entire supply chain. Customer communications, such as inquiries, feedback or complaints, are also a significant source of dark data. This information could provide valuable insights into customer expectations, areas for service improvement, and perceived quality (Chen and Liao, 2023; Guo et al., 2024; Ribeiro, et al., 2022).

However, their often unstructured nature – emails, chat messages, or calls – makes it difficult to extract useful information without the use of natural language analysis technologies. Maintenance logs, both for vehicles and warehouse equipment, generate a significant amount of data that can be critical to optimizing preventive maintenance, reducing downtime, and increasing equipment longevity. However, many of these logs remain in paper format or are not digitized, making them difficult to access and analyze. Supplier transactions are another significant source of dark data. Supplier interactions, including invoices, contracts, and delivery reports, generate a wealth of data that can be used to improve supply chain management, optimize costs, and ensure regulatory compliance. However, the fragmented nature of this data makes it difficult to integrate it into business management systems, limiting its usefulness for strategic decisions. The biggest challenge in extracting value from dark data in logistics and warehouses is precisely its unstructured nature. While structured data can be easily organized in tables and databases, dark data often requires advanced technologies to be analyzed effectively. Artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms can help identify hidden patterns and transform raw data into useful information, but this requires investments in technological infrastructure and specialized skills. Most companies, however, are faced with the complexity of this data without having the resources to manage it effectively. In conclusion, dark data in logistics and warehousing offers significant potential to improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and optimize supply chain management. However, its unstructured nature and the complexity in extracting useful information pose a significant challenge. Companies that can

leverage this potential by adopting advanced technologies and integrating data into their decision-making processes will have a significant competitive advantage (Zandbiglari et al., 2021; Mukherjee et al., 2023; Sabbagh and Ameri, 2020).

6. Optimizing Dark Data for ESG Compliance

6.1 Environmental Optimization

Dark data is an underutilized resource that offers significant opportunities to improve environmental sustainability in logistics and warehouse management. It is continuously generated by different sources such as sensors, telematics systems and RFID devices, but is often not analyzed systematically. If properly exploited, it can provide critical information to optimize the use of resources, reduce environmental impact and make operations more efficient and sustainable. An example of how dark data can contribute to sustainability is the analysis of energy use within warehouses. IoT sensors present in the facilities collect data on energy consumption patterns, monitoring parameters such as lighting, heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, and equipment use. This data, when analyzed, can reveal inefficiencies or excesses in energy consumption. For example, a deep analysis could show that certain areas of the warehouse are lit even when there are no personnel present, or that HVAC systems are operating at full capacity during hours when they are not needed. Using algorithms and AI tools, these systems can be automatically adjusted, significantly reducing energy consumption and, consequently, the associated greenhouse gas emissions. Another area where dark data can have a positive impact is in the optimization of transportation routes. Vehicles used for logistics are equipped with telematics systems that collect detailed data on routes, fuel consumption, traffic conditions, and weather conditions. This information can be combined and analyzed to plan more efficient routes. For example, data on traffic patterns could indicate that certain routes are congested at specific times of the day, suggesting less congested alternatives. Or, fuel consumption analysis could reveal which routes require more energy due to uneven terrain or frequent stops. By optimizing transportation routes based on this data, companies can significantly reduce fuel consumption, contributing to a reduction in CO2 emissions and greater environmental sustainability. Dark data also plays a crucial role in inventory management and waste reduction. In warehouses, RFID systems and sensors continuously monitor inventory, collecting data on product quantities, movements, and conditions. However, much of this information remains unused. By analyzing this data, companies can more accurately manage inventory levels, reducing excess inventory and preventing product spoilage. For example, dark data can reveal that certain items are being held in storage for too long or that certain products tend to spoil more quickly in specific environmental conditions. This information allows them to adjust inventory management and plan for demand in advance, avoiding wasted resources and minimizing the environmental impact of unused or spoiled goods. An additional benefit of using dark data for sustainability is the ability to accurately forecast demand. By analyzing historical data on transactions, deliveries and consumption trends, companies can make more accurate forecasts and adjust their operations accordingly. This can reduce the overproduction and overstocking of goods, thereby minimizing the waste of natural

resources and materials. Additionally, more efficient inventory management can lead to a decrease in the use of packaging, further reducing environmental impact. In summary, dark data offers a wide range of opportunities to improve environmental sustainability in logistics and warehouses. Detailed and targeted analysis of this data allows for optimizing resource use, reducing waste, and minimizing environmental impact. Companies that know how to leverage this information not only improve their operational efficiency, but also help create more sustainable and environmentally responsible logistics practices (Minashkina and Happonen, 2023; Chen and Liao, 2023; Perotti and Colicchia, 2023).

6.2 Social and Work-Related Considerations

Dark data is an underutilized resource that offers significant opportunities to improve environmental sustainability in logistics and warehouse management. It is continuously generated by various sources such as sensors, telematics systems, and RFID devices, but is often not analyzed systematically. If properly leveraged, it can provide critical insights to optimize resource use, reduce environmental impact, and make operations more efficient and sustainable. An example of how dark data can contribute to sustainability is the analysis of energy use in warehouses. IoT sensors in the facilities

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Dark data also plays a crucial role in inventory management and waste reduction. In warehouses, RFID systems and sensors continuously monitor stock, collecting data on product quantities, movements and conditions. However, much of this information remains unused. By analyzing this data, companies can more accurately manage inventory levels, reducing excess inventory and preventing product spoilage. For example, dark data can reveal that certain items are stored too long or that certain products tend to spoil more quickly in specific environmental conditions. This information allows them to adapt inventory management and plan for demand in advance, avoiding wasted resources and minimizing the environmental impact of unused or spoiled goods. An additional benefit of using dark data for sustainability is the ability to accurately forecast demand. By analyzing historical data on transactions, deliveries and consumption trends, companies can make more accurate forecasts and adapt their operations accordingly. This reduces the excessive production and storage of goods, thereby minimizing the waste of natural resources and materials. In addition, more efficient inventory management can lead to a decrease in the use of packaging, further reducing environmental impact. In summary, dark data offers a wide range of opportunities to improve environmental sustainability in logistics and warehousing. Detailed and targeted analysis of this data allows for the optimization of resource use, reduction of waste, and minimization of environmental impact. Companies that know how to leverage this information not only improve their operational efficiency, but also help create more sustainable and environmentally responsible logistics practices (Ribeiro et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022; Ahmand et al., 2021).

6.3 Governance and Transparency

Optimizing dark data in the context of corporate governance is a strategic process that allows organizations to ensure compliance with regulatory standards while building trust and transparency with their stakeholders. This approach is crucial to reduce legal risks and improve corporate reputation in an environment where environmental, social and governance (ESG) regulations are increasingly relevant. Effective governance dark data management allows for real-time compliance monitoring and accurate ESG reporting, which is essential to maintaining a solid reputation and building trust. One of the most relevant areas is monitoring regulatory compliance. Dark data related to shipping records, environmental reports or internal audits are often hidden in unstructured formats, such as paper documents, emails or non-integrated databases. This data, if properly collected and analyzed, can provide real-time information on the compliance of business operations with current regulations. For example, a company operating in the logistics sector can collect and analyze dark

data from shipping records to monitor in real time compliance with customs and safety regulations. By analyzing this data, potential violations can be identified early, thereby reducing the risk of fines, penalties, or legal disputes that could damage the company's image. This proactive approach allows companies to mitigate legal risks and build a reputation for trustworthiness and transparency. Another key area for dark data optimization is ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) reporting, which is becoming increasingly important to investors, customers, and other stakeholders. Much of the data needed to create comprehensive and effective ESG reporting exists in dark data formats, such as carbon records, ethical sourcing documents, or labor assessments. If left unexplored, this data represents a missed opportunity for companies to demonstrate their commitment to sustainability. Through dark data analytics, organizations can produce more accurate and detailed ESG reports that accurately reflect their environmental and social impact. For example, analyzing dark data on energy consumption, collected through IoT sensors or internal reports, can provide clear insights into a company's carbon emissions and progress toward sustainability goals. This transparency in reporting not only helps meet regulatory and investor demands, but also helps build strong trust with the public and customers, who are increasingly interested in corporate social responsibility. The ability to extract value from dark data for governance is not limited to regulatory compliance and ESG reporting, but extends to overall data management and information security. Dark data may contain sensitive or strategic information that, if not properly managed, can become vulnerable to security breaches or non-compliant use. Careful and structured analysis of dark data allows companies to identify data security gaps and implement appropriate measures to protect critical information. This is especially important in the context of privacy regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which require careful and transparent handling of personal data. Dark data optimization can therefore help prevent security breaches and ensure that the company operates in compliance with data protection regulations. In conclusion, dark data optimization in the context of corporate governance not only ensures regulatory compliance, but also improves transparency and builds trust with stakeholders. Through real-time monitoring of operational data and accurate ESG reporting, companies can demonstrate their commitment to sustainability and social responsibility. This approach not only reduces legal and operational risks, but also strengthens corporate reputation, helping to create a lasting bond of trust with the market and the community (Yeoh, 2021; Srour, 2022; Zhao, 2022).

7. Technologies to Unlock the Potential of Dark Data

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) is essential for analyzing and optimizing dark data, especially in the context of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) goals. These technologies offer significant potential for managing large quantities of unstructured and complex data that would otherwise remain unexplored. AI and ML enable the identification of hidden patterns, operational inefficiencies, and improvement opportunities in line with sustainability, transparency, and social responsibility. For instance, machine learning algorithms can analyze data from various sources to predict future demand, allowing companies to optimize inventory and reduce waste. Similarly, these algorithms can be employed to optimize transportation routes, reducing fuel consumption and carbon emissions. Another relevant aspect is the use of machine learning to improve energy management systems. IoT sensors in corporate facilities can continuously collect data on energy usage, machine consumption, and other operational parameters. When analyzed using AI tools, this data can reveal inefficiencies that might otherwise go unnoticed. For example, machine learning can identify unnecessary peaks in energy consumption and suggest solutions to automatically adjust the use of energy resources, thereby reducing operational costs and environmental impact. Natural Language Processing (NLP), a specific branch of artificial intelligence, is equally crucial for analyzing dark data, particularly textual and unstructured data. Textual data from corporate emails, internal documents, or social media interactions contain valuable information that is often overlooked

due to its complexity. Using NLP tools, it is possible to analyze these texts to uncover useful insights regarding supplier performance, internal company dynamics, or customer communication, all of which impact compliance with ESG goals. For example, NLP can be used to analyze contracts with suppliers to ensure they meet sustainability standards or to identify potential issues related to ethical practices along the supply chain. IoT and cloud-based solutions represent another cornerstone in the optimization of dark data and sustainability management. IoT sensors, installed within warehouses, production plants, or vehicles, continuously collect data on various variables such as energy usage, waste production, worker safety, and environmental conditions. This data can be combined and stored on cloud platforms, where it can be analyzed in real time. This type of real-time monitoring allows companies to take immediate action to reduce environmental impact or improve employee safety. For example, if an IoT sensor detects an abnormal increase in temperature in a section of a facility, the cloud-based system can immediately notify the responsible personnel, enabling a rapid response to prevent failures or accidents. The scalability of cloud solutions is particularly useful when managing large amounts of dark data, which often come from multiple sources and in various formats. Cloud platforms allow for the efficient storage and processing of this data, without physical or infrastructural limitations. Thanks to these technologies, companies can implement advanced analyses that identify recurring patterns, predict future trends, and improve operational management in line with ESG criteria. Cloud solutions not only facilitate access to and analysis of data but also allow for seamless integration of different data sources, improving overall transparency and efficiency. In summary, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing, and IoT technologies combined with cloud solutions are key tools for optimizing dark data in ESG management. Through these technologies, companies can transform untapped data into concrete opportunities to improve environmental sustainability, optimize logistical operations, and increase the transparency of their practices. These innovations enable businesses to align with ESG goals, reducing environmental impact, improving safety, and building trust with stakeholders through responsible and transparent governance (Chen, et al., 2022; Micu, et al., 2020; Kataria, et al., 2023).

8. Steps to Implement Dark Data Optimization for ESG

Data mapping is the first crucial step in fully leveraging dark data within the logistics and warehouse management ecosystem. This phase involves identifying all the sources of untapped data that exist within business operations, coming from various technologies and processes. These sources may include telematics systems installed in vehicles to monitor routes and fuel consumption, IoT sensors

in warehouses to track environmental conditions or energy efficiency, as well as internal communications such as emails or operational reports. Often, these data are generated in massive quantities and remain largely unused because they are scattered across different systems or stored in unstructured formats. Mapping dark data allows for a comprehensive overview of the available information resources and helps to determine which data could offer strategic value if properly analyzed. Once the data have been mapped, it is essential to proceed with data integration. This phase involves using a centralized data platform capable of aggregating information from various sources, structuring it into uniform formats, and making it accessible for further analysis. Data integration resolves one of the main obstacles in managing dark data, namely the fragmentation of information. Without a centralized platform, the data remain isolated in their silos, making it difficult to correlate information from different sources and obtain a holistic view of business operations. Once the data are integrated and organized, they can be easily analyzed by advanced tools, contributing to the improvement of both logistics operations and compliance with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) standards. The next step is the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and predictive analytics technologies to the aggregated dark data. These tools can process large amounts of information and identify complex patterns that may escape manual analysis. For example, AI can help pinpoint inefficiencies in logistics processes, such as suboptimal transportation routes or excessive energy use in warehouses. Additionally, ML can be used to predict future trends, such as changes in demand or potential supply chain issues, allowing the company to anticipate problems and take corrective action before they turn into significant costs or risks. Predictive analysis can also support operational optimization to improve compliance with ESG standards, identifying areas where the company can reduce its environmental impact or improve working conditions, such as employee safety and efficient resource use. Finally, continuous monitoring and reporting are essential to ensure that the insights gained from dark data analysis are effectively applied and lead to tangible improvements. This process includes monitoring business performance against ESG goals and analyzing data in real time to detect changes or new inefficiencies. The collected and analyzed information must be used to generate accurate and transparent reports for internal and external stakeholders, including regulatory bodies and investors. Transparency in reporting not only demonstrates compliance with ESG commitments but also helps strengthen stakeholder trust by showing how dark data have been used to enhance the company's sustainability and social responsibility. In summary, optimizing dark data requires a well-structured strategy that begins with mapping and integrating available information, followed by the application of advanced AI and ML technologies to identify inefficiencies and opportunities. Continuous monitoring of progress and the creation of transparent reports are crucial to ensuring that the insights gained contribute concretely to improving ESG performance and regulatory compliance. This strategy allows companies to fully exploit the hidden value of dark data, enhancing operational efficiency and promoting more sustainable and responsible management (Chen and Liao, 2023; Mariappan et al. 2023; Wang and Peng, 2023).

9. Key Benefits of Dark Data Optimization for ESG

Improving sustainability is one of the main objectives that can be achieved by fully leveraging dark data in business management. These often-unused data can provide valuable insights into how to reduce waste and optimize resource use. For example, by analyzing data collected from IoT sensors installed in a warehouse, it is possible to identify inefficiencies in energy consumption, such as unnecessary lighting or excessive use of heating, ventilation, and air conditioning systems. This information can lead to better management of energy resources, resulting in reduced electricity consumption and lower carbon emissions. In this way, the company can decrease its environmental footprint, contributing to more sustainable logistics aligned with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) goals. Cost savings is an additional direct benefit from optimizing dark data. Business operations, especially in logistics and warehousing, are often characterized by hidden inefficiencies that do not emerge in traditional data. Through in-depth analysis of dark data, opportunities to reduce operational costs can be identified. A concrete example is the optimization of transportation routes using vehicle telematics data, which allows for the selection of more fuel- and time-efficient routes. Similarly, better inventory management, achieved through data from RFID systems, can reduce waste by limiting excess stock and improving demand planning. All of these strategies lead to more efficient resource use and, consequently, lower operational costs, improving company profitability. Improving compliance is another key aspect that can be strengthened by using dark data. Regulations and ethical standards, particularly in the ESG realm, are becoming increasingly stringent, and companies must be able to demonstrate their adherence through accurate data and reports. Continuous analysis of dark data, such as shipment logs, communications with suppliers, and operational data, enables real-time monitoring of compliance with current regulations. This not only helps prevent potential violations but also allows companies to be proactive in adapting to new regulations. This approach reduces legal risks and ensures that the company operates in compliance with ethical and regulatory standards, strengthening its competitive and reputational position. Finally, increased transparency is a significant advantage derived from dark data analysis. Transparency is a crucial component in managing stakeholder relationships, especially regarding ESG reporting. Insights from dark data enable the creation of more detailed and accurate reports, providing a clear and comprehensive view of a company's environmental, social, and governance performance. These transparent reports strengthen stakeholder trust, including investors, customers, and regulators, as they demonstrate a concrete commitment to sustainability and social responsibility. The ability to provide accurate, data-driven information not only meets compliance requirements but also creates a competitive advantage, as companies that can demonstrate strong commitment to ESG goals are increasingly valued in the market. In conclusion, the effective use of dark data has a profound impact on several critical areas of business management, from sustainability to cost savings, from regulatory compliance to increased transparency. By analyzing these untapped data, companies can not only improve their logistics and warehouse operations but also strengthen their position with stakeholders, promoting a more ethical, transparent, and sustainable business model. These benefits translate into an overall improvement in business performance, both operationally and reputationally (Alsayegh, et al., 2020; Saxena, et al., 2022; Duran, and Tierney, 2023).

10. Conclusions

Optimizing dark data for ESG compliance represents a significant strategic opportunity in logistics and warehouse management. Thanks to technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and advanced analytics, companies can transform untapped data into valuable resources to improve environmental sustainability, strengthen social responsibility, and ensure solid governance practices. Dark data, often hidden in various systems or unstructured, contains information that, when analyzed, can reveal inefficiencies, consumption patterns, and operational trends, paving the way for targeted interventions that reduce waste, optimize resource use, and enhance operational transparency. By using AI, for example, companies can analyze vast volumes of dark data to identify patterns that suggest opportunities to reduce energy consumption, thus improving the sustainability of logistics operations. IoT enables real-time monitoring of operational conditions in warehouses and along the supply chain, allowing prompt responses to any deviations from ESG standards, such as excessive resource consumption or suboptimal working conditions. The integration of these advanced technologies also allows companies to anticipate regulatory requirements, providing precise and timely data to demonstrate compliance. Unlocking the potential of dark data not only helps meet but also exceed ESG goals. Organizations that can leverage this data to improve operational efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and ensure ethical and transparent practices can distinguish themselves in the global market, earning the trust of investors and customers. As a result, operations become not

only more efficient but also more ethical and aligned with the growing expectations for sustainability and social responsibility.

11. Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDMs	Clean development mechanisms
CDR	Corporate digital responsibility
CFP	Corporate financial performance
CO2	Carbon dioxide
CSP	Corporate sustainability performance
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DSR	Design Science Research
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governane
EU	European Union
FCM	Fuzzy cognitive map
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HR	Human Resources
HVAC	Heating, ventilation and air conditioning
IIoT	Industrial of Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IPOs	Initial public offerings
IRGTM	Integrated Reporting for Growth and Transformation Management
LED	Light Emitting Diode
ML	Machine Learning
MNCs	Multinational corporations
MNEs	Multinational enterprises
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OPEX	Operational excellence
RFID	Radio-Frequency Identification
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SEC	Securities Exchange Commission
SISME	Sustainable value for competitive advantage in small and medium enterprises
SMEs	Small and medium enterprises
TCFD	Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures

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